

Geographic Exploration of the HDI in Mexico (2018–2021)

Alfredo C. Perez Ortiz¹, Marlen Hernandez Ortiz², Imelda Ortiz Medina³, Jorge Martinez Perez⁴

¹Graduate of the Postgraduate Program,

^{2,3,4}Universidad Autónoma de Zacatecas (UAZ).

ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
31 May 2025

Corresponding Author:
Marlen Hernandez Ortiz

KEYWORDS: IDH, QGIS, COVID-19, México.

ABSTRACT

Aim of this study is to analyze the Human Development Index (HDI) of Mexico by federal entities before and during the COVID-19 pandemic through a geographic comparison. The annual measurement for each state in the country is based on a methodology proposed by the Human Development Research Office, which takes into account health, education, and income indices. The geographic representation of the results is carried out using the Geographic Information System (GIS), specifically the QGIS software. The results indicate that the HDI values of the states fall within the ranges reported by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), with the most significant downward trends observed in the health and income indicators. Therefore, this contribution may serve to expand studies related to the HDI for the federal entities of the Mexican Republic in the context following the COVID-19 health contingency.

INTRODUCTION

The Human Development Index (HDI) is a measure developed by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) since the 1990s, aimed at determining people's quality of life based on factors beyond economic income, primarily including health and education (Flores & Allcca, 2022). Its purpose is to identify societies around the world that need to improve their human development situation (Ortiz Medina et al., 2020).

In Mexico, the national well-being index, the HDI, is reported annually based on the methodology proposed by the UNDP, and less frequently for certain federal entities, municipalities, households, and individuals (UNDP, 2015). The most recent HDI by state in the Mexican Republic was published in 2020 (UNDP, 2022). Given the interest and, therefore, the objective of this study—to analyze the changes in the HDI of Mexican states before and during the COVID-19 pandemic—it is necessary to obtain HDI data for the missing years in the 2018–2021 period. These values will be calculated and presented in this article, along with their geographic representation to support comparative analysis.

Although there are ongoing efforts to incorporate new variables into HDI measurement—such as the HDI adjusted for planetary pressures (PHDI), which considers environmental quality as a factor in human development (Conde Pardeiro, 2023)—this contribution aims to support sustainable human development aligned with the 2030

Agenda, which promotes growth in dignified and equitable environments with protected biodiversity (UNDP, 2022). This scientific paper is based on the traditional HDI analysis reported by the UNDP, while also acknowledging the current context and variety of emerging HDI-related metrics.

Returning to the analysis of HDI by federal entities in Mexico, there is a study that clearly shows an increase in HDI between 2008 and 2012 across all states of the Mexican Republic, except for Baja California Sur, which experienced a decline in the education component during the analyzed period. However, in general, all states in both years reported an HDI above the medium human development threshold of 0.612, and most surpassed the global average of 0.700—except for Puebla, Veracruz, Michoacán, Oaxaca, Guerrero, and Chiapas in 2008. By 2012, the first three of these had risen above the global average (UNDP, 2015). This analysis will be consistently discussed throughout our results section, to maintain continuity in examining HDI changes across each Mexican state.

Additionally, the 2022 UNDP report (UNDP, 2022) compares the income, education, and health subindices for Mexican municipalities as reported in 2015 and 2020. This provides indirect insight into the changes caused by the COVID-19 pandemic in specific locations.

Other documents that will inform the discussion in this study include those published by the UNDP addressing development in Mexico in the context of COVID-19 during

2020 and 2021 (Leal et al., 2020; Martínez and Sulmont, 2021). The results presented in those reports are generalized at the national level and do not break down the impacts across individual Mexican states. They cover issues ranging from shortages of medical supplies in hospitals to the economic toll on businesses forced to close or scale back operations. They also include early findings related to inequality in Mexico’s education system (UNDP, 2022; Sulmont and Martínez, 2022), along with other relevant studies (UNDP, 2018; Aguilar Ortega, 2019; Gutiérrez-Valdez, 2021).

Body text

The first task to be carried out is the search for HDI data by federal entity in Mexico, with available measurements found only for the year 2020. Therefore, equation (1) proposed by the UNDP (2015) is used, as it was applied in reporting the HDI for the federal entities in that same year.

$$IDH = (IS * IE * II)^{1/3} \tag{1}$$

where:

IS is the health index, measured using life expectancy at birth by federal entity as reported by the National Population Council (Conapo, for its acronym in English), considering reference values between 20 and 85 years (Conapo, 2020), and calculated using equation (2).

$$IS = \frac{\text{life expectancy} - \text{minimum value}}{\text{maximum value} - \text{minimum value}} \tag{2}$$

IE is the education index, which in this case is calculated using the average years of schooling for individuals aged 25 and older. The minimum value for schooling is zero, and the maximum is fifteen. This information is obtained from the main statistics of the national education system, documented by the General Directorate of Planning, Programming, and Educational Statistics (SEP, 2023). Equation (3) presents this indicator.

$$IE = \frac{\text{averages years of schooling} - \text{minimum value}}{\text{maximum value} - \text{minimum value}} \tag{3}$$

II is the income index, determined using equation (4), where GNI refers to the Gross National Income per capita adjusted in U.S. dollars (USD) based on Purchasing Power Parity (PPP). The data is obtained from the National Institute of Statistics and Geography (INEGI, 2018–2021), using income figures by federal entity from the Socioeconomic Conditions Module of the National Household Income and Expenditure Survey. In this case, the minimum income value is 100 and the maximum is 75,000.

$$II = \frac{\ln(INB) - \ln(\text{minimum value})}{\ln(\text{maximum value}) - \ln(\text{minimum value})} \tag{4}$$

Once the HDI has been obtained by federal entity of Mexico in the established period (2018–2021), the database is imported into the QGIS software version 3.28.4.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The HDI results for the federal entities of Mexico calculated in this study are very similar to those published in official UNDP documents for the years 2008, 2010, and 2012 (UNDP, 2015), and they fall within the average range (0.5–0.85) used to categorize the municipal HDI across all states of the Mexican Republic for the year 2020 (UNDP, 2022). Figure 1 presents four maps of Mexico, each showing the state-level HDI for one year within the 2018–2021 period. The colors of the states represent the different HDI levels: low HDI (white, around 0.6–0.69), medium HDI (pink, between 0.67 and 0.743), high HDI (orange, 0.743–0.758), and very high HDI (red, 0.758–0.83).

In the Figure 1, it is observed that from 2018 to 2019, the state of Sonora dropped from a high to a medium HDI category, and Zacatecas and Tlaxcala dropped from medium to low HDI. This occurred before the COVID-19 pandemic. However, comparing these results with 2020—the year when economic activities were suspended due to health measures—no state reached a very high HDI level. Coahuila, Nuevo León, Campeche, and Mexico City lost that category and fell to the high HDI level, with Mexico City dropping even further to the medium level. Notably, Tlaxcala rose back to the medium HDI level.

By 2021, when 69.4% of the population in Mexico had completed their vaccination regimen (Martínez & Sulmont, 2021) and there was potential to reactivate the economy, this year can still be considered part of the pandemic. From 2022 onward, we could speak of the post-pandemic period—a topic not addressed in this work due to the lack of available data to calculate the GNI. Therefore, in the final year of the pandemic, 2021, we observe further state-level HDI changes. Hidalgo, Morelos, Yucatán, and once again Tlaxcala fell to the low HDI level, while Coahuila, Nuevo León, Campeche, and Mexico City regained their very high HDI status. This suggests that most states remained within the same HDI level during the pandemic, and the most notable changes occurred in states that were previously in the very high category but experienced a decline during the health crisis and a subsequent recovery during the control phase. This was not the case for Zacatecas; and although Hidalgo, Morelos, and Yucatán maintained their levels until 2020, they declined in the final year of analysis.

It is important to highlight that, under the methodology used, the HDI values for the federal entities are relatively low compared to the national HDI reported by other sources, which themselves differ from one another (UNDP, 2018; UNDP, 2019). A similar situation occurs with the HDI classification for Mexican municipalities, as calculated and reported by the UNDP (2022), again due to methodological variations. Additionally, there is a clear mismatch in the state-

“Geographic Exploration of the HDI in Mexico (2018–2021)”

level HDI ranges in Mexico, and caution should be exercised when making comparisons (UNDP, 2015). This is also supported by a geographic analysis of ten variables that meaningfully explain municipal development in the state of Guanajuato. That study, methodologically aligned with this work, uses the “natural breaks” classification system, which produces standardized differences among classification intervals based on an algorithm that minimizes standard deviations (Heald, 2018).

It is also worth mentioning that, during the analyzed period—similar to what was published by Aguilar Ortega (2019)—there was a reduction in HDI disparities between states, clearly influenced by the COVID-19 health emergency. In that study, Mexico City was highlighted as having the highest HDI and Chiapas the lowest, a pattern observed in the years 2000, 2010, and 2015. However, this trend does not align with the results for the analyzed period. Although Chiapas consistently showed a low HDI across all four years, it was not the lowest-ranked state. The same applies to Mexico City, which, despite reducing its category in 2020, was not the top performer during the entire period.

Figure 1. Maps of the Mexican Republic with State-Level HDI (2018–2021).

Source: Own elaboration based on data from CONAPO (2020), SEP (2023), and INEGI (2018–2021).

As mentioned in the Introduction, the Human Development Index (HDI) is a set of parameters or indices that support the measurement of qualitative or value-based phenomena centered on human dignity. This dignity is not only measured in monetary terms, but also includes aspects such as years lived in good health and an education solid enough to enable individuals to live maturely and in harmony with both the living and non-living components of nature, as well as the world’s cultural and social systems (UNDP, 2018). Therefore, the components that make up the HDI are analyzed

in this study to determine the reasons behind the changes observed before and during the COVID-19 pandemic.

We begin with the Education Index (EI). Figure 2 shows maps of the Mexican Republic where states are classified into different EI ranges. No federal entity falls within the low EI level (0.4 – 0.46); only three states—Sonora, Nuevo León, and Mexico City—are in the very high EI category (0.67 – 0.76). Chihuahua, Michoacán, Guanajuato, State of Mexico, Oaxaca, and Veracruz fall into the medium EI classification (0.47 – 0.56). Therefore, the remaining 23 states are classified as having a high EI (0.57 – 0.66).

What stands out in this result is that there were no changes in EI categories among the Mexican states throughout the study period. This suggests that the pandemic did not impact the indicators of Mexican education, despite the fact that teaching and learning online posed a major societal challenge (Leal et al., 2020). This implies that the Education Index did not directly influence the changes observed in the HDI of Mexican states during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Figure 2. Education Index (EI) of Mexican States (2018–2021).

Source: Own elaboration based on data calculated from SEP (2023).

The second index analyzed in the discussion of Mexico’s HDI by federal entity is the Income Index (II) (see Figure 3). The classification ranges are divided into five categories: very low (0.49–0.51), low (0.51–0.61), medium (0.61–0.71), high (0.71–0.81), and very high (0.81–0.9). In this case, significant changes occurred during the pandemic. That is, prior to the pandemic (2018 and 2019), there were no category shifts in the II. However, in 2020, notable differences emerged. Baja California Sur, Sonora, Nuevo León, and Colima dropped from the high to the medium level. Those that fell from the medium to the low level included San Luis Potosí,

“Geographic Exploration of the HDI in Mexico (2018–2021)”

Guanajuato, Morelos, Colima, and Yucatán. Additionally, the states of Guerrero and Oaxaca declined one level further, entering the very low II range.

Several states remained within the medium, low, and very low statuses, but only the state of Campeche consistently remained in the very high II category through 2021—this is reflected in Campeche’s HDI, except in 2020.

In 2021, some states regained their previous categories, including Nuevo León, Sinaloa, Durango, San Luis Potosí, Guanajuato, Guerrero, Oaxaca, and Yucatán. It’s noteworthy that the II of Tabasco remained unaffected during the first three years of the study period. Even more, in the second year of the pandemic, it rose to the high level.

This income variable is also evaluated by the UNDP in its report *“Development in Mexico and COVID-19: A Challenge One and a Half Years Into the Health Emergency”* (Martínez & Sulmont, 2021), where it is discussed that the decline in income led to an increase in informal employment and reduced consumption in Mexico. In fact, this indicator generated the greatest inequality in HDI during the pandemic (Gutiérrez-Valdez, 2021).

Figure 3. Income Index (II) of Mexican Federal Entities (2018–2021).

Source: Own elaboration based on data calculated from INEGI (2018–2021).

Lastly, the index considered within the studied HDI is the Health Index (IS). Figure 4 presents four maps of the IS for the states of the Mexican Republic corresponding to the years of study. From 2018 to 2019 (pre-pandemic), the states of Chihuahua, Michoacán, Guanajuato, Tlaxcala, Veracruz, Oaxaca, Campeche, and Yucatán dropped one level in the IS, moving down to the 0.75–0.80 range, which is categorized as

low. This low level had not been recorded for any Mexican state in 2018, although neither had the very high level (above 0.89).

In 2020, the year the pandemic began, all federal entities declined one level, except for Mexico City and those already in the low category. By 2021, most states regained one level of IS—17 to be exact—while 14 remained at the same level as the previous year, and Mexico City dropped one level. One of the largest cities in the world was unable to recover a year and a half into the pandemic, compared to other states in the country. Managing the economy of states with relatively small populations is not the same as managing those with populations several times larger.

Figure 4. Health Index (IS) of the States of the Mexican Republic (2018–2021).

Source: Own elaboration with data calculated from Conapo (2020).

Systematizing the discussion of the results, the Human Development Index (HDI) of Mexico’s federal entities reflects significant changes both prior to and during the COVID-19 pandemic, primarily affected by the Health Index (IS) and the Income Index (II). As noted by Leal and collaborators (2020), the former was impacted by the lack of hospital infrastructure, and the latter by the economic slowdown caused by nationwide inactivity during the health crisis.

In contrast, the Education Index (IE) did not show changes for any state in the country (relative to the measurement interval considered), despite the digital divide that emerged. However, this last indicator remains open for further debate, as nationwide reports did identify general educational setbacks during the pandemic (Sulmont and Martínez, 2022). It is worth noting that terminal efficiency rates in primary,

secondary, and high school increased during the school years spanning from 2019 to 2021.

CONCLUSION

The contribution of this study makes it possible to identify the most vulnerable federal entities in Mexico before and during the COVID-19 pandemic based on the HDI for the recent years 2018–2021. This opens the door to future lines of research, such as an in-depth analysis of the decision-making processes carried out within both state and federal public policies to reduce and address the setbacks that emerged during the health crisis caused by the pandemic. Additionally, this study complements the HDI results commonly reported by the UNDP.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to express their gratitude to the institutions that provided access to the data used in this study, including CONAPO, SEP, and INEGI. Special thanks are also extended to the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) for their methodological guidance on the Human Development Index. Especially to SECIHTI for their support through the postgraduate scholarship granted to the main author of this work.

REFERENCES

1. Aguilar Ortega, T., (2019). Desarrollo humano y desigualdad en México. *México y la Cuenca del Pacífico*, 8(22), 121-141.
2. Consejo Nacional de Población (Conapo). 2020. Indicadores demográficos de México de 1950 a 2050. Disponible en http://www.conapo.gob.mx/work/models/CONAPO/Mapa_Ind_Dem18/index_2.html
3. Conde Pardeiro, M., (febrero 2023). Relación entre el IDH y el IDHP: hacia un índice de desarrollo humano más sostenible. <https://hdl.handle.net/10902/28495>
4. Flores, J., & Allcca, G. (2022). Índice De Desarrollo Humano (IDH), ingresos y gasto público, en Moquegua 2008 al 2017. *Revista Ciencia Y Tecnología Para el Desarrollo-UJCM*, 5(1), 55-69.
5. Gutiérrez-Valdez, O. M. (2021). Desigualdad e inequidad social: resultados de la pandemia en México 2020-2021. *eseconomía*, 16(54), 33-43.
6. Heald, J. (2018). Del IDH al análisis geográfico del desarrollo desigual a través de un paisaje de indicadores. *Acta Universitaria*, 28 (NE-1), 42-56. doi: 10.15174/au.2018.1866
7. Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Geografía (INEGI). (2018, 2019, 2020, 2021). Encuesta Nacional de Ingresos y Gastos de los Hogares (ENIGH). Módulo de Condiciones Socioeconómicas (MCS). Recuperado de <https://www.inegi.org.mx/programas/enigh/nc/2018/>
8. Leal, V., Martínez, C., & Sulmont, A. (2020). Desarrollo Humano y COVID-19 en México: Desafíos para una recuperación sostenible. Programa de las Naciones Unidas para el Desarrollo (PNUD). <https://www.mx.undp.org/content/mexico/es/home/library/poverty/desarrollo-humano-y-covid-19-en-mexico-.html>
9. Martínez, C., & Sulmont, A. (2021). Desarrollo en México y COVID-19: Desafíos a un año y medio del inicio de la contingencia sanitaria. <https://www.undp.org/es/mexico/publications/desarrollo-en-m%C3%A9xico-y-covid-19-desaf%C3%ADos-un-a%C3%B1o-y-medio-del-inicio-de-la-contingencia-sanitaria>
10. Ortiz Medina, I., Hernández Ortiz, M., & Martínez Pérez, J. (2020). Producto Interno Bruto e Índice de Desarrollo Humano dos variables inconexas. *Revista de Ciencias Sociales*, 29(44), 97-116.
11. Programa de las Naciones Unidas para el Desarrollo (PNUD). (2015). Índice de Desarrollo Humano para las entidades federativas, México 2015. Avance continuo, diferencias persistentes. México: Programa de las Naciones Unidas para el Desarrollo. Recuperado de http://www.mx.undp.org/content/dam/mexico/docs/Publicaciones/PublicacionesReduccionPobreza/InformesDesarrolloHumano/pnud_boletinIDH.pdf
12. Programa de las Naciones Unidas para el Desarrollo (PNUD). (2018). Índices e indicadores de desarrollo humano, actualización estadística de 2018. Nueva York: Programa de las Naciones Unidas para el Desarrollo. Recuperado de <chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/http://hdr.undp.org/system/files/documents/2018humandevelopmentstatisticalupdateespdf.pdf>
13. Programa de las Naciones Unidas para el Desarrollo. (2019). Informe sobre Desarrollo Humano 2019. Más allá del ingreso, más allá de los promedios, más allá del presente: Desigualdades del desarrollo humano en el siglo XXI. Nueva York: Programa de las Naciones Unidas para el Desarrollo. Recuperado de chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/http://hdr.undp.org/system/files/documents/hdr2019espdf_1.pdf
14. Programa de las Naciones Unidas para el Desarrollo (PNUD). (2022). Informe de desarrollo humano municipal 2010-2020: una década de transformaciones locales para el desarrollo de México. México: Programa de las Naciones Unidas para el Desarrollo. Recuperado de

<https://www.undp.org/es/mexico/publicaciones/informe-de-desarrollo-humano-municipal-2010-2020-una-decada-de-transformaciones-locales-en-mexico-0>

15. Secretaría de Educación Pública (SEP). (2023). Principales cifras, sistema educativo de los Estados Unidos Mexicanos. Recuperado de <https://www.planeacion.sep.gob.mx/estadisticaeindicadores.aspx>
16. Sulmont, A., & Martínez, C. (2022). COVID-19 y educación en México: primeras aproximaciones de una desigualdad agudizada. <https://www.undp.org/es/mexico/publications/covid-19-y-educacion-en-mexico-primeras-aproximaciones-de-una-desigualdad-agudizada>